

A STUDY OF FINANCIAL LITERACY AND FINANCIAL BEHAVIOUR AMONG MILLENNIALS AND GENERATION Z

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Abstract

Financial activities are vital to the achievement and growth of every economic system. In recent years, financial literacy has become a top priority around the world. The financial sector offers a wide range of products in a complicated and worldwide economy, and product distribution has also risen. This has pushed individuals to have the essential financial awareness and understanding in order to make the most use of their available capital. This research aims to identify the financial literacy level among millennials and Generation Z. For the study data was collected from the 109 respondents using a structured questionnaire. As per findings among millennials and Generation Z knowledge about the financial market and products is not encouraging as only 11% of respondents have excellent knowledge while 40% of respondents have average knowledge. In terms of investment among millennials and Generation Z - fixed deposits, savings deposits, and insurance are more popular around 40% of respondents invest in shares and Mutual funds. The findings indicate that the internet and Televisions are the most effective source in creating financial literacy among millennials and Generation Z.

Keywords : Financial Literacy, Financial Behaviour, Millennials, Gen Z, Investment, Financial education

Introduction

Education is an essential component of our daily lives. The knowledge required to make crucial financial judgments is known as financial education. Financial education refers to the capacity to perceive and apply a wide range of financial concepts, such as personal financial planning and budgeting. It is an individual's capacity to use their learning, abilities, and expertise to make critical decisions about their own finances in order to achieve long-term financial stability for themselves and their family. On a daily basis, people come into contact with and engage with the financial world. Financial literacy has become important in making decisions about all aspects of our daily lives. The ability to grasp financial products in a variety of formats, as well as financial attitude, both represent our financial education. (Lusardi, 2019) An essential indicator of people's ability to make financial decisions is their level of financial literacy.

In light of the financial sectors and the overall economy's rapid changes and advances, it's critical to know whether people are well-equipped to manage the maze of financial decisions they face on a daily basis. Financial planning is a continuous process and a strategy to achieve planned goals. Generally, your earnings and spending enable you to regulate investments, which means knowledge to manage your money to reach your financial goals. (R & Rathod, 2021) Financial literacy is defined as the ability to understand and manage money and the management of personal finance. Financial literacy is the foundation of your connection with money, and it is a lifelong learning adventure. Budgeting and investing, as well as numerous financial capabilities, are understood and used successfully.

(Choudhary & Kamboj, 2017) Because of the increased market complexity, exposure to Fin-tech such as mobile and digital payments, the shift from defined retirement plans to contributory plans, and concern for saving for retirement and medical services, it is critical to understand financial concepts to perform sound financial decisions. Financial education improves consumers' willingness and ability to manage their finances for safe future prospects.

This study aims to analyze the financial literacy among the Millennials and Generation Z. (DIMOCK, 2019) Working definition of Millennials is equivalent in age span those are born between the time periods 1981 to 1996. While Generation Z includes all those people who are born between the time period 1997-2012. (Bhushan & Medury, 2013) Individuals with financial education are better able to make better financial decisions. A big improvement in the financial knowledge of

individuals is necessary. This can be accomplished by providing appropriate financial education programmes to the right people at the right time.

Review of Literature

(Thavva, 2021) According to the findings of the study, (64 percent) have a reasonable level of financial literacy. This is an encouraging indicator. Basic literacy concepts such as simple interest, inflation, credit cards, and savings interest rate are well understood by 80 %. Only 56% of those polled understand advanced literacy topics including long-term returns, stock market movements, risk/return on stocks/bonds, and diversification. Financial literacy has also been shown to improve people's skills and capacities to make better decisions and, as a result, to lead to more favorable financial behavior.

(Antony & Jospheh, 2021) Financial literacy is essential for achieving financial inclusion because it allows people to have more access to financial services and make informed decisions about how to use their money. Education with a focus on financial management can surely lead to a higher degree of competency, allowing each individual to respond to the ever-changing economic landscape of their neighborhood and the country as a whole. The level of financial inclusion can be increased by developing an effective delivery mechanism that is complemented by appropriate financial products and financial counseling.

(PK & Reddy, 2020) Financial literacy is a critical component of every country's economy. Despite our best efforts, the level of financial literacy among our country's citizens is not very high. Adding fundamental financial literacy concepts to the school curriculum can help raise financial literacy levels by allowing children to learn the concept at a young age and teaching their parents if they are illiterate. Advanced financial literacy principles can be incorporated into the higher education curriculum to provide students with in-depth knowledge of financial goods.

(Mändmaa, 2019) Financial literacy has evolved into a crucial life and work skill. Gender, nationality, age, and academic subject all have an impact on students' financial literacy. However, the level of education that students pursue, their work experience, and their parents' level of education have little bearing on their financial literacy. The study's primary findings were that financial literacy among Estonian students was low and that students' interest in long-term planning was low. Only 3.4 percent of respondents manage their financial affairs several years ahead of time, while 55.9% have considered pension savings.

(Choudhary & Kamboj, 2017) In recent years, financial literacy has become a top priority around the world. According to the research, only 1/3 of the whole sample has higher financial literacy. Even though the majority of people have basic financial knowledge and engage in constructive financial behavior, 57% of respondents have a negative financial outlook. This shows that policymakers should take steps to change people's minds. However, sociodemographic data reveals that certain characteristics may impede people from becoming more financially educated. Low income, economic instability, and young age are all linked to poor financial literacy.

(Sekar & Gowri, 2015) According to the study, the overall financial literacy level of 50.90 percent among all respondents is not encouraging. The current generation's financial behavior has been influenced by early purchases made with credit cards. The need for proper financial literacy and financial awareness becomes unavoidable. It may be inferred that financial literacy is influenced by gender, education, income, marital status, and the number of dependents, but not by age.

(Mihalčová, Csikósová, & Antošová, 2014) Financial literacy is an important factor in making decisions in all aspects of our lives. Financial literacy is defined as the ability to comprehend financial goods with which most people come into touch. Because the lack of financial literacy is a global issue, it is necessary to plan actions regarding financial advancement. Financial literacy has increased slightly (scores went from 56 % to 62.5%) as has the trend of financial education and a more responsible approach by consumers themselves, according to a comparison of survey findings from 2007 and 2012.

Objectives of Study

1. To measure the level of financial literacy among the millennials and Gen z.

2. To analyze the level of awareness among millennials and Gen Z regarding various financial products.
3. To examine the millennials and Gen z Investment Behaviour among different Financial Products
4. To find out the association between millennials and Gen z gender and investment frequency.
5. To find out the association between level of income and saving for retirement planning.

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis has been framed.

H0: There is no significant association between Gender and Investment frequency.

H0: There is no significant association between level of income and saving for retirement planning.

Research Methodology

To analyze the financial literacy among the millennials and Gen z data was collected using the purposive sampling technique. Data for the research was collected using both primary and secondary sources. A 5-point Likert scale was used to assess the impact of several factors on financial literacy among the respondents, with 1 indicating "never" and 5 indicating "always".

Primary Source – A structured questionnaire was forwarded to the respondents digitally and in an offline mode. The purposive sampling technique was used to select 109 respondents for the study, of which 51 were male and 58 were female.

Secondary Source – In secondary sources data was collected through the various books, journals, and newspapers.

For the analysis and interpretation of data Frequency table, Descriptive statistics, Cronbach Alpha, Chi-Square Test, Mean, and Standard Deviation.

Analysis & Interpretation

		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	51	46.78
	Female	58	53.22
Age-group	15-23 years	33	30.28
	24-32 years	45	41.28
	33-40 years	31	28.44
Level Of Education	Intermediate	3	2.75
	Graduate	55	50.49
	Post Graduate	38	34.86
	M.Phil & PhD	13	11.93
Monthly Income	Up to Rs.10,000	36	33.02
	Rs.10000 – 20000	12	11.01
	Rs. 20,000 40,000	26	23.85
	Rs. 40,000 – 60,000	20	18.35
	Above Rs. 60000	15	13.76
Occupation	Salaried	41	37.61
	Student	44	40.37
	Housemaker/Housewife	10	9.17
	Self Employed	14	12.85

The aim was to analyse the demographic profile of the respondents. As per data collected 53.22% of respondents are female followed by 46.78% Male. In terms of age group, 41.28 % of respondents belong to the 14-32 years age group followed by 30.28 % of respondents belonging to the 15-23 years age group. In terms of the level of education, most of the respondents are graduates (50.49%) followed by 34.86 % who have a post-graduate degree. Most of the respondents belong to up to Rs. 10000 monthly income group followed by 23.85% of respondents from Rs. 20000 – 40000 income group. In terms of occupation, 40.37 % of respondents are students followed by 37.61% salaried employees, 12.85% self-employed, and 9.17% homemakers/housewives.

Chart 1 - Financial Literacy Level among Millennials and Generation Z

From the above figure it can be concluded that overall financial literacy level among millennials and Generation Z is not encouraging. As 40 % of respondents have an average knowledge about the financial market and products followed by 38 % of respondents with good knowledge. The results conclude that financial literacy among millennials and Generation Z is not adequate.

Table 2 – No. of Respondents using the following banking products.

	YES	NO
Debit Card	89.9%	10.1%
Credit Card	39.4%	60.6%
UPI	81.7%	18.3%
Internet Banking	74.3%	25.7%
Savings Account	90.8%	9.2%
Current Account	15.6%	84.4%
Fixed Deposit	67.9%	32.1%

The aim was to analyze the respondent's perception towards the different banking products and services. The results suggest that 89.9% of the respondents use Debit Card but the number of millennials and Gen Z using Credit Card is as low as 39.4%. In terms of digital payment millennials and Gen Z have favourable perceptions as 81.7% of respondents use UPI and 74.3% of respondents use Internet Banking. In terms of account facilities offered by banks, saving account deposits are used by almost 90.8 % of millennials and Gen Z respondents while Fixed deposits are preferred by 67.9% of respondents.

Table 3 – Respondent’s Investment Behaviour among different Financial Products

	YES	NO
Shares	40.4%	59.6%
Mutual Fund	35.8%	64.2%
Fixed Deposits	65.1%	35.9%
Insurance	57.8%	42.2%
Bonds & Debentures	26.6%	73.4%
NPS & Provident Fund	21.1%	78.9%
Savings Deposit	87.2%	12.8%

The aim was to identify the respondent’s investment behaviour toward different financial products. As per findings, 40.4% of respondents prefer to invest in shares, 35.8% of respondents invest in mutual funds, 65.1% of respondents invest in Fixed deposits, 57.8% of respondents invest in insurance, 26.6% of respondents invest in Bonds & Debentures, 21.1% respondents invest in NPS & Provident fund while 87.2% respondents invest in Saving deposit. The results suggest that millennials and Gen Z have a low perception of investment in NPS & Pension Funds, Bonds, and Debentures while a high perception as investment options towards Savings deposits, Fixed deposits, Insurance, and a medium perception towards Shares and mutual funds.

Table 4 – Investment Frequency * GENDER Crosstabulation

			GENDER		Total
			MALE	FEMALE	
Investment Frequency	Monthly	Count	27	26	53
		Expected Count	24.8	28.2	53.0
	Quarterly	Count	11	13	24
		Expected Count	11.2	12.8	24.0
	Half Yearly	Count	4	8	12
		Expected Count	5.6	6.4	12.0
	Annually	Count	9	11	20
		Expected Count	9.4	10.6	20.0
	Total	Count	51	58	109
		Expected Count	51.0	58.0	109.0

H0: There is no significant association between Gender and Investment frequency.

Table 5 - Chi-Square Test (Investment Frequency * GENDER)

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.275 ^a	3	.735
Likelihood Ratio	1.295	3	.730
Linear-by-Linear Association	.564	1	.453
N of Valid Cases	109		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.61.

- As per the results P-value is .735 which is greater than 0.05. Hence null hypothesis is accepted.
- The findings of the Chi-Square test indicate that there is no significant association between gender and investment frequency. Thus, it can be concluded that investment frequency doesn’t depend upon Gender.

Table 6 – Sources of Awareness effectiveness in providing information regarding financial products and schemes.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Television	109	1.00	5.00	3.4771	1.02376
Internet	109	1.00	5.00	4.1835	1.04673
News Paper	109	1.00	5.00	3.3761	.97931

Magazine	109	1.00	5.00	2.8257	1.19291
Valid N (listwise)	109				

The aim was to identify the effectiveness of different sources of awareness in providing information regarding financial products and schemes. The findings indicate that the Internet is the most effective source in creating financial literacy followed by Television and newspapers, while Magazines are less effective in creating financial literacy among millennials and Generation Z.

Table 7 – Financial Behaviour (Descriptive Statistics)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
On a regular basis, I keep track of my expenses.	109	1.00	5.00	4.146	.92121
I pay my credit card bills and loan installments on time.	109	1.00	5.00	4.357	1.04989
Every month, I prepare a budget.	109	1.00	5.00	3.807	1.27277
I save some part of my income as retirement planning	109	1.00	5.00	3.697	1.27297
I save some part of my income to meet uncertainties.	109	1.00	5.00	4.082	1.17164
Valid N (listwise)	109				

Here: 1 – Never, 2 – Rarely, 3 – Sometimes, 4 – Usually, 5 – Always.

Table 8 – Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.818	5

The aim was to analyse the financial behaviour of respondents related to various financial aspects. The results indicate that millennials and Generation Z have favourable financial behavior as they usually track their expenses, prepare a budget monthly, and save some part of their income to meet uncertainties while always preferring to pay their loan and installments on time. While sometimes most of the respondents prefer to save some part of their income for retirement planning.

Table 9 - Saving part of the income as retirement planning * Income Level Crosstabulation

		Income Level					Total
		Up to Rs. 10000	Rs. 10000 - Rs. 20000	Rs. 20000 - Rs.40000	Rs. 40000 - Rs. 60000	Above Rs. 60000	
Saving part of the income as retirement planning	Never	7	0	1	0	0	8
	Rarely	5	1	4	2	0	12
	Sometimes	4	4	11	4	2	25
	Usually	12	2	2	3	5	24
	Always	8	5	8	11	8	40
Total		36	12	26	20	15	109

H0: There is no significant association between level of income and saving for retirement planning.

Table 10 – Chi-Square Tests (Saving part of the income as retirement planning * Income Level)

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	32.568 ^a	16	.008
Likelihood Ratio	35.589	16	.003
Linear-by-Linear Association	9.760	1	.002
N of Valid Cases	109		

a. 17 cells (68.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is .88.

- As per the results P-value is .008 which is less than 0.05. Hence null hypothesis is rejected.
- The findings of the Chi-Square test indicate that there is a significant association between level of income and savings for retirement plans. Thus, it can be concluded that income level influences the motive for savings for retirement planning.

CONCLUSION

The results of the above analysis indicate that overall financial literacy among millennials and Generation Z is low. According to the findings, 40% of respondents have average knowledge of the financial market and products, while 38% have excellent knowledge. The findings show that millennials and Generation Z lack adequate financial literacy. According to the findings, 89.9% of respondents use debit cards, but only 39.4% of millennials and Gen Z use credit cards. Millennials and Gen Z have positive attitudes toward digital payments, with 81.7 % using UPI and 74.3 % using Internet Banking. The results indicate that millennials and Generation Z have favourable financial behaviour as they generally monitor their expenses, prepare a budget monthly, and save some part of their income to meet uncertainty and risk even while opting to pay their loan and installments regularly. It has been also found that the Internet, followed by television and newspapers, is the most effective source for millennials and Generation Z to develop financial literacy, while magazines are less effective. Overall, financial literacy among millennials and Generation Z is low, and the government should take steps to raise awareness about financial aspects.

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